

THE FUNCTIONAL EVIDENCE WORKSHOP 2023

ACTIVITY RESULTS SUMMARY REPORT

Thank you to all of the participants in the Functional Evidence Workshop!

Summary

Functional evidence can be incorporated into variant classification when evaluating the pathogenicity of a genetic variant. Functional data however is one of the least used categories of evidence, meaning functional data represents an untapped resource for resolving uncertainty in diagnostic genomics. The MAVE Education Project aims to support increased use of functional data/evidence, especially with the increasing body of high throughput functional data. The MAVE Education project recently delivered the first investigative workshop, entitled “Functional Evidence and how to use it”. This report summarises the results from the [2023 Functional Evidence Workshop Activity](#), information collected to sample participant opinions on how the participants (you and your peers) consider and use functional evidence.

What are functional assays?

We asked the participants to define functional assays. While nearly all of the participants provided definitions using the term ‘assay’ or ‘effect’, there was a large variation in how people defined and considered functional data. We then aimed to survey the participants’ use and understanding of the concept of assay class, as defined in (Brnich et al., 2019). When asked for examples of functional assays, participants gave many different answers, covering many assays across many systems, methods and ‘readout’ types. Ultimately, functional assays cover a large and broad array of types, and the workshop participants are using assay data across the breadth of assay class.

The workshop revealed that assay class is an area that many find complex. We suggest that the concept of assessing assay class revolves around determining if the assay in question is really a model for the disease mechanism you are curating against. The MAVE Education will work to collate advice on how to assess assay class, and whether an assay is appropriate for use in variant classification.

How to find functional evidence?

We asked participants how they find functional evidence.

Figure 1. Methods used by Functional Evidence Workshop participants to find functional evidence for variant classification

Mastermind is used by a very large proportion of the participants when searching for functional data for a specific variant; Mastermind identifies variant-specific literature, but the functional assays within the variant search results must be manually identified. ClinVar was also identified as a commonly used search tool and ClinVar variant pages include a Functional Evidence field, however this field does not appear comprehensive yet (for e.g. the example variant lists only one of the 11 publications that include functional data on the variant). The MAVE Education project will investigate improved methods for identification of variant relevant functional data.

The Case Study: BRCA1 c.5246C>G Pro1749Arg

In the workshop we presented a variant case example, the VARIANT: BRCA1 c.5246C>G Pro1749Arg). Two functional assays were discussed in the workshop.

Audience assessment of Scully et al. 1999

A functional assay from Scully et al. was presented ([Scully et al., 1999](#) PMID:10635334).

Assay Description (from workshop)

- HCC1973 (BRCA1 mut) breast cancer cell line gamma irradiation sensitivity assay
- Retroviral introduction of either wildtype or variant BRCA1
- What function is being tested? BRCA1 DNA repair after irradiation
- Is that function relevant to pathogenicity in humans? Breast cancer derived cell line with an assay readout relevant to DNA repair

While the majority of participants thought that the assay in Scully et al. 1999 was applicable for use as functional evidence, a small number considered this assay either an inappropriate model of disease (i.e. was not the right type of assay for evaluating disease mechanism) (Figure 2A) or invalid (results were not reliable enough to apply) (Figure 2B). When asked to apply evidence, a third of the participants were not confident enough to apply this data as evidence (Figure 2C). In addition, there was some variation in opinion as to the strength of this evidence; three participants indicated that

they thought this evidence may be moderate strength (Figure 2D), though (Brnich et al., 2019) recommendations would be that this assay is sufficient for supporting evidence at most.

Figure 2. The Functional Evidence Workshop participants opinion on the use of functional data in Scully et al. 1999 for classification of BRCA1 c.5246C>G Pro1749Arg

Audience assessment of Findlay et al. 2018

We next presented results from a well-known high throughput assay, ([Findlay et al., 2018](#)) [PMID:30209399](#).

Assay Description (from workshop)

- Saturation genome editing (SGE) of BRCA1
- Cell viability assay
- Performed in HAP1 (haploid) cells, variant construct selection as readout (SNV read loss = loss of function)

Most participants believed that Findlay et al. 2020 could be used for OddsPath calculation and most participants agreed that this experiment could be used as evidence towards pathogenicity. However, there was large variation between participants on the strength of evidence to apply (C).

Figure 3. The Functional Evidence Workshop participants opinion on the use of functional data in Findlay et al. 2018 for classification of BRCA1 c.5246C>G Pro1749Arg

Conclusions

The activity performed in the Functional Evidence Workshop shows variation in how expert diagnostic scientists find, consider and apply functional evidence in variant curation.

Based on the results of the workshop activity, and aligned with ACMG/AMP recommendations as per (Brnich et al., 2019; Richards et al., 2015), the MAVE Education project aims to:

- Collate and share information resources on use of functional evidence in variant classification, including expert recommendations.
- Investigate the best methods for identifying functional data relevant to a specific variant
- Investigate the concept of assay class and how it is used to assess assays with an aim to build recommendations for assay evaluation.

Thank you to all of the participants in the Functional Evidence Workshop, your consultation is very helpful in guiding the direction of the MAVE Education project. If you have any questions on the activities of the MAVE Education project team, please contact Rehan Villani, Project co-ordinator, rehan.villani@qimrberghofer.edu.au.

References

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